

The impact of climate change on the reliability of rubble mound berm breakwaters considering the correlation among design parameters

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluates the reliability of rubble mound berm breakwaters in the Port of Tombak, located in Iran, examining the direct impact of climate change and the importance of considering and applying the correlation between design parameters on the hydraulic performance of these structures. Using the Copula function and Monte Carlo Sampling, it was found that the correlation between design parameters significantly affects the probability of breakwater failure. The results indicate that sea level rise due to climate change dramatically increases the probability of breakwater failure. These findings highlight the necessity of using probabilistic design methods to improve accuracy and reduce uncertainties in the design of rubble mound berm breakwaters.

Keywords: *Rubble mound berm breakwater, Reliability, Copula, Monte Carlo, Climate change*

1 INTRODUCTION

Breakwaters are essential for ensuring safety in marine operations and protecting coastlines by reducing wave and current impacts. Rubble mound berm breakwaters offer economic and technical advantages, including lower costs and smaller stones in the armor layer. A critical aspect of their design is estimating wave overtopping and its impact on hydraulic performance. Several empirical relationships for estimating wave overtopping in rubble mound berm breakwaters have been proposed (Eurotop, 2007; Eurotop, 2018; Sigurdarson and Van Der Meer, 2012; Sigurdarson and Van Der Meer, 2016). The high variability of experimental data introduces considerable uncertainty into these empirical relationships. Consequently, employing probabilistic design methods, such as the Monte Carlo method, can help mitigate these uncertainties and enhance design accuracy (Hosseini and Ahmadi, 2020). In breakwater research, assuming independence among input random variables is common, but this assumption may not hold due to complex interrelationships. The copula function models dependencies between random variables, offering more accurate reliability analysis. Climate change, particularly rising sea levels, impacts the hydraulic performance and failure probabilities of these structures (Church and Clark, 2013; Galassi and Spada, 2014).

2 METHODOLOGY AND STUDY CASE

This study focuses on the Tombak Export Service Port on the northwestern coast of the Persian Gulf, with coordinates approximately E 52.203 and N 27.702. The primary objective is to evaluate the failure probability of rubble mound berm breakwaters in the area, considering climate change and environmental variations. The breakwater in this port includes an 8-meter-wide berm is positioned at a level of 3 meters above Chart Datum (CD), while its base is situated at a depth of 8.87 meters below CD, contributing to the overall stability of the structure against wave action. Statistical methods, including copulas and Monte Carlo sampling, were employed to analyze long-term data on wave height, wave period, and water level. The best-fit copula distribution was determined to describe parameter dependencies. Failure probabilities were calculated using various models and MATLAB code, accounting for both correlated and independent design parameters. An overtopping limit of $10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}/\text{m}$ was set, and the effect of increased water levels due to climate change was also assessed.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Based on the correlation assessment conducted on design data using MATLAB, and considering the evaluation of copula families based on NSE and RMSE parameters, the best copula for the variable pairs examined is shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. Additionally, the best D-Vine copula structure selected to represent the correlation between design variables is displayed in Figure 1.

Table 1. Results of best Pair Copulas Fitting for data pairs (WL-Tp-Hs)

data pairs	copula Family	copula parameter	RMSE	NSE
Hs-Tp	Frank	7.562	2.2071	0.9977
WL-Tp	Gumbel	1.0219	0.1728	0.9999
Hs-WL	Frank	-0.1246	0.1769	0.9999

Figure 1. (a) Best Pair Copulas Fitting on data pairs (WL-Tp-Hs). (b) The appropriate D-vine structure (1-2-3) for three Hs, Tp, and WL variables.

The study highlights that accounting for correlations between environmental parameters using a D-vine copula affects the failure probability of the rubble mound berm breakwater. The largest difference in failure probability between correlated and independent parameters was observed with the Sigurdarson and Van der Meer (2012) formula, showing a 3.16% difference, while the Eurotop (2007) formula showed the smallest difference at 0.05% (Figure 2 (a)). Additionally, with a projected 36 cm sea-level rise over the next 100 years due to climate change, the failure probability of the breakwater increased by up to 6.4% for the Eurotop (2007) model and by 0.42% for the Sigurdarson and Van der Meer (2016) model. Under rising sea levels, the maximum difference in failure probability between correlated and independent parameters was 2.875 %, again with the Sigurdarson and Van der Meer (2012) formula (Figure 2 (b)). These findings emphasize the need to consider both parameter correlations and sea-level rise when assessing breakwater failure probabilities.

Figure 2 (a) The failure probability of the berm breakwater based on different overtopping relations. (b) The failure probability of the rubble mound berm breakwater under increased sea level in different overtopping models.

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